

Heart rate variability for training readiness assessment

Renato Fonseca
Data Science and Intelligent
Analytics
University of Applied Sciences
Kufstein
Kufstein, Austria
2110837169@stud.fh-
kufstein.ac.at

ABSTRACT

The strive to achieve new best performances is an intrinsic characteristic of humans. While training hard to succeed in sport can be seen as an admirable trait, too much sport without adequate recovery can be detrimental to the desired progress and lead potentially to fatigue and injury. The body embarks into a state of overtraining, where it has no chance of convalesce from intense and repetitive training. With the advent and propagation of wearables the collection of physiological data turned into a large-scale process. In almost every device heart rate variability (HRV) is gathered along other metrics. Changes at HRV may indicate an overtraining state. HRV combined with other parameters can be utilized as a basis for the use of machine learning techniques in order to detect patterns and predict training readiness.

KEYWORDS

Heart rate variability, overtraining, stress, machine learning

1 Introduction

The search for a healthy lifestyle can demand a high physiological toll if signs of fatigue are overseen. Training performance can be affected in case of the body being not able to cope with the training load due insufficient recovery time. Overtraining or chronic fatigue can imply severe consequences for athletes at all levels.[1] Overtraining can be differentiated from overreaching, which stands for a short-term overtraining and normally can be resolved within two weeks of adequate recovery [1]. The differences between both overtraining states are according to [2] not always clear, since overtraining itself can be considered a relative term due to individual characteristics regarding physical fitness and genetic predisposition. The prevention of overtraining can be executed by detecting and evaluating physical fatigue accurately [3]. An objective detection of overtraining is a difficult task since fatigue turns to be mostly a subjective feeling. HRV can be a helpful tool in order to overcome this challenge [4]. In order to introduce into the properties of heart rate variability, diverse articles have been reviewed, with the purpose assessing the potential of a systematic evaluation of HRV and how machine

learning techniques can be used in order to make exercise fatigue visible.

2 Heart rate variability

Heart Rate Variability is defined by the time variation between following heartbeats. This so-called inter-beat interval is never constant, varying also when the heart rate seems to be in a stable state [5]. Parameters from HRV can be used as basis while analyzing the Autonomic Nervous System (ANS), since any kind of physiological or psychological stimuli will imply changes on the ANS. The ANS represents a control system for unconscious actions from the body. Examples for these actions are among others the cardiac function, respiration, digestion, blood pressure and urination [6].

Figure 1: The calculation of HRV is based on the inter-beat intervals in ms, with R standing for the spike of a heartbeat and RR for the interval between spikes [11].

2.1 Heart rate variability analysis

HRV can be evaluated using different approaches. Linear methods like time domain or frequency domain and non-linear methods such as Poincaré-Plot analysis are the most common ways. The time-domain analysis is characterized by its simplicity, using two normal-to-normal heartbeat peaks (NN) as basis and measuring the fraction of time between them. For the Frequency domain analysis takes the heart-rate signal and focus on its periodic oscillations. NN heartbeats are decomposed into distinctive frequency zones, being quantified relatively to the quotient of power to intensity. Finally, the Poincaré-plot describes in a scatter plot the relationship between a pair of consecutive heartbeats over a time series [5].

Figure 2: A typical Poincaré Plot of RR intervals [13].

2.2 Examples of HRV parameters

This section will briefly introduce some common HRV parameters that can be normally used as input variables in machine learning procedures.

2.2.1 Time domain parameters

SDNN: the standard deviation between NN within a time period as the square root of the variance of NN intervals [12].

With

$$\mathbf{RR}_{\text{mean}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{RR}_i}{N}$$

$$\mathbf{SDNN} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mathbf{RR}_i - \mathbf{RR}_{\text{mean}})^2}{N - 1}}$$

SDSD: the standard deviation of the differences between two consecutive NN intervals [12]

With:

$$\mathbf{RR}_{\text{diff}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |\mathbf{RR}_i - \mathbf{RR}_{i+1}|}{N - 1}$$

$$\mathbf{SDSD} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (|\mathbf{RR}_i - \mathbf{RR}_{i+1}| - \mathbf{RR}_{\text{diff}})^2}{N - 1}}$$

RMSSD: the square root of the root mean square of the sum of all differences between consecutive NN intervals [12].

$$\mathbf{RMSSD} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\mathbf{RR}_{i+1} - \mathbf{RR}_i)^2}{N - 1}}$$

NN50: the number of pairs of succeeding NN intervals that differ by more than 50 ms in the full recording [12].

$$\mathbf{NN50} = \sum_{i=1}^n \{ |\mathbf{RR}_{i+1} - \mathbf{RR}_i| > 50\text{ms} \}$$

pNN50: the percentage of successive intervals that differ by more than 50 ms [12].

$$\mathbf{pNN50} = \frac{\mathbf{NN50}}{N} \times 100\%$$

2.2.2 Frequency domain parameters

Frequency domain parameters can be constituted from different frequency components of the heartbeat signal such as VFL, LF, HF and LF/HF [5].

VFL: Very low frequency signals between 0.003 and 0.4 Hz

LF: Low frequency signals between 0.4 and 0.15 Hz

HF: High frequency signals between 0.15 and 0.4 Hz

LF/HF: The ration of low to high frequency

2.2.3 Nonlinear parameters

The Poincaré-plot analysis is based quantitatively on fitting an ellipse on the plotted shape, with the center of the ellipse being the average RR interval [12]. The plot is typically constituted of two components called SD1 and SD2. SD1 is described by the standard deviation of the points perpendicular to the line of identity, standing for the short term beat to beat variability. On the other hand, the SD2 component is defined by the standard deviation of the points along the line-of-identity, describing the long-term beat to beat variability [12].

$$SD_1 = \sqrt{\text{Variance}(S_1)}$$

$$SD_2 = \sqrt{\text{Variance}(S_2)}$$

With

$$S_1 = (RR_i - RR_{i+1})/2 \quad RR_i = (RR_1, RR_2, \dots, RR_{N-1})$$

$$S_2 = (RR_i + RR_{i+1})/2$$

$$RR_{i+1} = (RR_2, RR_3, \dots, R$$

2.3 The relationship between HRV and recovery

Recovery defines the processes that take place in the human body in order to perform a transition into the state before exercise [5]. Ideally this state transition leads to an adaption due to the supercompensation resulted from the stress level caused by the exercise. The continuous assessment of the stress level is vital in order to avoid overtraining [5]. Monitoring the fatigue level after exercise is usually a time-consuming task, being characterized by its invasive nature. HRV represents a non-invasive, comfortable and affordable way to picture the current status of fatigue and infer how good the athlete is recovering [5], since different HRV parameters are directly affected by intense training and decrease during the activity [8].

3 Use cases of Machine Learning (ML) with HRV

Machine learning describes the model-based extraction of relevant information and patterns from data based on inter-domain relationships [9]. This section briefly introduces some uses of machine learning techniques for the detection stress states of the body. HRV analysis with machine learning can anticipate the rise of diseases while helping with the allocation of patients into the right treatment and therapies [6]. According to [10], models trained exclusively on HRV can detect fatigue with accuracy scores between 75% and 91%. Using the support vector machine (SVM) fatigue could be detected with an accuracy of 80% while algorithms tested on resting HRV data could reach an accuracy of 75% for fatigue detection [10].

3.1 HRV analysis with Random Forest

Classification algorithms can be utilized to distinguish between fatigue and non-fatigue states. For this purpose, algorithms are trained on resting HRV data separately from task related HRV data. Resting HRV data are consequently labeled as non-fatigue while the other dataset is labeled with the “fatigue” state [10]. By means of time domain features a random forest classifier can be used to classify stress, reaching a mean accuracy of 73% [10]

3.2 HRV analysis with Adaboost

According to [6] Alhithary et al. was able to classify stress conditions by means of the Adaboost algorithm. An accuracy of 93% was achieved and further physiological parameters were utilized as features, such as respiration, skin temperature, accelerometer and Electrocardiogram data.

3.3 HRV analysis with Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

Based on the work of He et al. [10] describes the possibility of classifying cognitive stress based on real-time features that were captures in very short 10 s intervals. Based on non-linear features a CNN was used to understand and extract relevant features from the input layer containing a 0.04-20 Hz signal band. The use of CNN enables the possibility of remote monitoring HRV in a more efficient and easier way, while at the same time facilitating the extraction of valuable features from raw Electrocardiogram signals [10].

Figure 3: Typical architecture for HRV classification with CNN [6].

4 Conclusion

The papers examined for this abstract could give a first impression how the evaluation of heart rate variability with machine learning can possibly help the understanding of the own body’s physiological state, with the evaluation of stress levels as an indicator for training readiness. Considering the possibilities offered by smartphones and wearables nowadays such as collecting data with embedded sensors in a centralized way, this physiological evaluation can lead to rational recommendations on which training load could be ideally targeted. Being able to objectively assess the body readiness can lead a possible athlete to an increased productivity and to a higher sense of self-awareness.

REFERENCES

- [1] Baumer et al: Heart Rate Variability, Blood Pressure Variability, and Baroreflex Sensitivity in Overtrained Athletes. *Clin J sport Med* 2006;16:412-417
- [2] Buchheit M, Simon C, Piquard F, et al. Effects of increased training load on vagal-related indexes of heart rate variability: A novel sleep approach. *Am J Physiol Heart Circ Physiol*. 2004;287:H2813-2818.
- [3] Ni, Z.; Sun, F.; Li, Y. Heart Rate Variability-Based Subjective Physical Fatigue Assessment. *Sensors* 2022,22,3199. [https://doi.org/ 10.3390/s22093199](https://doi.org/10.3390/s22093199).
- [4] Williams S, Booton T, Watson M, Rowland D, Altini M. Heart Rate Variability is a Moderating Factor in the Workload-Injury Relationship of Competitive CrossFit™ Athletes. *J Sports Sci Med*. 2017 Dec 1;16(4):443-449. PMID: 29238242; PMCID: PMC5721172.
- [5] Udayanga, M.A.S., 2018. Heart Rate Variability (HRV) for sports and exercise training. *Sri Lankan Journal of Sports and Exercise Medicine*, 1(1), pp.13-18. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.4038/sljsem.v1i1.6>
- [6] Ishaque S, Khan N and Krishnan S (2021) Trends in Heart-Rate Variability Signal Analysis. *Front. Digit. Health* 3:639444. doi: 10.3389/fdgh.2021.639444
- [7] Correlations between the Poincaré Plot and Conventional Heart Rate Variability Parameters Assessed during Paced Breathing - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/A-typical-Poincare-Plot-of-RR-intervals-The-duration-of-the-current-cardiac-beat-RR-n_fig1_6537361 [accessed 6 Jan, 2023]
- [8] Makivić, Bojan, Marina Nikić Djordjević, and Monte S. Willis. "Heart Rate Variability (HRV) as a tool for diagnostic and monitoring performance in sport and physical activities." *Journal of Exercise Physiology Online* 16.3 (2013).
- [9] Murdoch, W. James, et al. "Interpretable machine learning: definitions, methods, and applications." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.04592* (2019).
- [10] Matuz, Andrés, et al. "Machine learning models in Heart Rate Variability based mental fatigue prediction: training on heterogeneous data to obtain robust models." (2022).
- [11] Izzah, Nailul, Auditya Purwandini Sutarto, and Mohamad Hariyadi. "Machine Learning models for the Cognitive Stress Detection Using Heart Rate Variability Signals." *Jurnal Teknik Industri* 24.2 (2022).
- [12] Mirescu, Stefan-Claudiu & Harden, Scott. (2016). NONLINEAR DYNAMICS METHODS FOR ASSESSING HEART RATE VARIABILITY IN PATIENTS WITH RECENT MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION. *Romanian Journal of Biophysics*. 22. 117-124.
- [13] Correlations between the Poincaré Plot and Conventional Heart Rate Variability Parameters Assessed during Paced Breathing - Scientific Figure on ResearchGate. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/figure/A-typical-Poincare-Plot-of-RR-intervals-The-duration-of-the-current-cardiac-beat-RR-n_fig1_6537361 [accessed 8 Jan, 2023].